

EVALUATION OF LOADING RATE DEPENDENCE ON FRACTURE BEHAVIOR OF CFRP LAMINATE WITH HIGH SPEED IMAGING

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1. Introduction

The objective of this study is to clarify the fracture behavior of CFRP under the high speed tensile loading. We selected the intermediate modulus and high strength CFRP laminate which is a typical material used in the aerospace field. The fracture process under high speed tensile loading was captured by a high-speed video camera. By using the latest high speed imaging techniques, the fracture process can be clearly observed. However the high speed imaging is qualitative evaluation and is not quantitative evaluation. The strain distribution is the important information in the evaluation of destruction phenomenon; therefore, we introduced Digital Image Correlation (DIC) into high speed imaging of CFRP fracture. We succeeded in the measurement of the surface deformation and the analysis of the strain by DIC.

2. Specimens and Experimental methods

2.1 Preparation of Specimens

The material used in this study was T800S/3900-2B (Toray) which is reinforced by intermediate modulus and high tensile strength carbon fiber and 180 °C cure type epoxy resin system (Table 1). We made three kinds of specimens. The specifications of specimens are shown as Table 2. The evaluation area is painted small random points by white ink. The GFRP tabs are adhered to prevent from the stress concentration by wedge grips. The overview of specimen was shown in Fig. 1.

2.2 Experimental and analytical methods

We used high speed tensile testing machine (*Hydroshot HITS-T10, Shimadzu Corp.*) with a load cell of 10kN capacity on high speed tensile test. The tensile speeds is up to 20 m/sec, and we selected to 10, 5.0, 2.0 m/sec of tensile speed.

We used high-speed video camera (*HyperVision HPV-X, Shimadzu Corp.*) for high resolution observation up to 10,000,000 frame per second (fps). Fracture of the specimen reduced load quickly. Monitoring at 1MHz for the decline of the load, when the load declined from the maximum to 50% of the maximum, a trigger signal was made from the pulse generator. The experimental setup was shown in Fig.2. We used flash lamp to get enough brightness in this study. The flash time is 2 milliseconds on this flash lamp. The flash lamp is brighter than the continuation illumination. The trigger signal for the flash lamp synchronized with start-up signal of the high speed tensile testing machine.

After the material testing and the high-speed imaging, we analyzed obtained high speed image by the DIC software (*Strain Master DaVis8.0.8, LaVision GmbH*). We should get calibration image at each test to introduce to DIC analysis in this study. We decided that the calibration images were the image before material test beginning. The specimen didn't load from testing machine to get the calibration image.

3. Results and discussions

Table 3 was shown measurement parameters for measurement equipments, and measurement results

3.1 Results of material test

Results of high speed tensile tests were shown in Fig. 3. The conspicuous speed dependence could not be confirmed on this tensile rate.

By comparison of between high speed tensile test and static tensile test, there were not difference in the maximum stress at [0]2 and [90]6 specimens. However, the maximum stress on high speed tensile test became smaller than that on static tensile test at [45/-45]S specimens. The static maximum stress was quoted from data base. This decline of maximum stress depended on the strain rate of the matrix resin. Generally, when the strain rate becomes high, the elasticity modulus, the strength and shear modulus become large on the general resin. The maximum stress decrease could have caused by the shear modulus increase at this strain rate. It should be consider the difference of the shape of the specimen on the static test from data base and the high speed tensile test. We need detailed examination about the cause of this maximum stress decrease.

3.2 Results of High speed imaging

The fracture images of high speed tensile test were shown in Fig. 4, 5, 6. We could succeed to capture the high speed images up to 1,000,000 fps.

We could see the fracture process resembled at [0]2 specimens about any tensile speed. These specimens were broken by a minute crack. The crack grew while cutting fiber. After a few micro seconds, splitting was observed in the specimen surface. The duration of fracture phenomenon can be estimated as less than 10 μ sec (10m/sec), 12 μ sec (5m/sec), 20 μ sec (2m/sec) in case of [0]2 specimens from high speed images.

We could see the fracture process resembled at [45/-45]S specimens about any tensile speed. The first crack started to grow from the edge of specimen to the other side. This crack was parallel to fiber direction. The duration of fracture phenomenon can be estimated as less than 12 μ sec (10m/sec), 12 μ sec (5m/sec), 20 μ sec (2m/sec) in case of [45/-45]S specimens from high speed images.

On [90]6 specimens, the first cracks were grown near GFRP tab. The duration of crack growing were 8 μ sec (10m/sec), 10 μ sec (5m/sec) 5 μ sec (2m/sec).

3.3 Results of DIC analysis

We analyzed the high speed images in the quantification by DIC analysis.

Fig 7, 8 and 9 are shown Stress – Strain from DIC curve. Strain values were analyzed from central part of the specimens of the high speed images.

Fig 7 and Fig 9 were shown that these specimens had linearity between stress and strain on this strain rate. The stress-strain curve showed good agreement for the straight line. The slopes on the graphs were similar to the other graphs at same laminate configuration without [45/-45]S specimens.

The other side, Fig 8 was shown the specimens had nonlinearity between stress and strain on this strain rate. Those curves had some inflection points. The temporary non-rise of load suggested the fractures occurred except surface. We thought that these fractures were crack occurrence from back side, peeling off the gluing surface (CFRP and GFRP tab) and delamination of specimen.

The images of the strain distributions which were calculated from DIC analysis were shown Fig. 11, 12 and 13. We excluded the area that the white paint point came off during the high speed tensile test before fracture. The strain increased with the elapse in the time at all specimens.

The strain was concentrated in the parallel to the direction of the fiber at [45/-45]S specimens. We could see the centralization with extreme strain on [45/-45]S Specimen surface, The 2nd layer in addition to the 1st layer, too. However, we could see the area of declined strain. This area was grown by the increase of the load. It is consider that this growth occurred with the delamination. It is considered that the effect of twist of the specimen appeared sensitively.

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Table 1. Properties of T800S/3900-2B

Manufacturer	Toray		
Carbon fiber	T800SC		
Matrix	Epoxy 3900-2B		
Volume functions [%]	55		
Strength [MPa]	3100		
Elastic modulus [GPa]	153		
Poisson's ratio	0.34		

Table 2. Specifications of the specimen

Layered	[0] ₂	[45,-45] _s	[90] ₆
Material	T800S/3900-2B		
Number of ply	2	4	6
Lf [mm]	80	80	80
Ls [mm]	20	20	20
W1 [mm]	6	8.1	8.0
T1 [mm]	0.42	0.82	1.22
Lt [mm]	30	30	30

Fig. 1. Overview of specimen

Fig. 2. Overview of Experimental system

Table 3. Measurement parameters and testing results

Layered	Tensile speed [m/sec]	Recording rate [fps]	Trigger frame number	Maximum stress [MPa]
0 UD	10	500k	128	3403.0
	5	250k	128	3226.9
	2	100k	128	3373.8
90 UD	10	500k	128	70.8
	5	500k	128	73.9
	2	1M	128	60.7
[45/-45] _s	10	500k	128	197.9
	5	250k	100	194.2
	2	100k	100	182.9

Fig. 3. Tensile rate – maximum stress curve

(A) 10m/sec, 500kfps

(A) 10m/sec, 500kfps

(B) 5m/sec, 250kfps

(B) 5m/sec, 250kfps

(C) 2m/sec, 100kfps

(C) 2m/sec, 100kfps

Fig 4. High speed images of high speed tensile fracture on $[0]_2$ specimens

Fig 5. High speed images of high speed tensile fracture on $[45/-45]_s$ specimens

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(A) 10m/sec, 500kfps

(B) 5m/sec, 500kfps

(C) 2m/sec, 1Mfps

Fig 6. High speed images of high speed tensile fracture on $[90]_6$ specimens

10m/sec

5m/sec

2m/sec

Fig 7. Stress-Strain curve form DIC results on $[0]_2$ specimens

10m/sec

10m/sec

5m/sec

5m/sec

2m/sec

2m/sec

Fig 8. Stress-Strain curve form DIC results on $[45/-45]_s$ specimens

Fig 9. Stress-Strain curve form DIC results on $[90]_6$ specimens

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Fig 11. DIC results at high speed tensile process on $[0]_2$

Fig 12. DIC results at high speed tensile process on $[45/-45]_s$

Fig 13. DIC results at high speed tensile process on $[90]_6$

4. Conclusion

- We could succeed the measurements on high speed tensile test, and high speed imaging for fractures of high speed tensile test. We could observe the fracture process on 3 type CFRP specimens with high speed video camera. We could quantify high speed images with DIC analysis.
- In to digital image correlation, we could quantify the high speed image on high speed tensile test. The temporal resolution of DIC depended on the frame rate of high speed imaging. In this high speed tensile test, we could get high speed image on the fracture of CFRP specimen at up to 2,000,000 frame per second with high speed video camera. The time resolution of the strain measurement by DIC analysis depends on the recording rate of high speed imaging.
- We suggested that the strength of [45/-45]S CFRP on high speed tensile test was lower than static tensile test. It was thought that the decline of the maximum stress was caused by the increase of the shear modulus. However, we couldn't consider the difference of the shapes of specimens. We should investigate in detail about these results.